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Between Policy and Practice: Institutional Barriers to Inclusive Employment for Visually Impaired College Teachers in Punjab, Pakistan

Ammara Chaudhry

MS Scholar, Department of Education, GC Women University, Sialkot
ammara.chaudhry2019@gmail.com

Tayab Ul Nisa

PhD Scholar, Department of Education, GC Women University, Sialkot
tayabulnisa@gmail.com

Dr. Yaar Muhammad

Associate Professor, Department of Education, GC Women University, Sialkot
Yaar.Muhammad@gcwus.edu.pk

Abstract

Public colleges in Punjab are legally committed to providing access facilities/environment and equal employment of teaching staff with disabilities in the National Inclusive Employment Framework, including the Higher Education Commission Policy for Students with Disabilities at Higher Education Institutions in Pakistan, and the Punjab Empowerment of Persons with Disabilities Act (2022). However, the institutional environment to translate these commitments into practice, as far as the affiliated college sector is concerned, is largely missing in Punjab. This is qualitative research that aimed to explore the link between 'Inclusive Employment Policy' with the lived professional realities of visually impaired college teaching staff of public colleges in Punjab, Pakistan. Data were collected through a semi-structured interview with ten purposively sampled visually impaired college teachers of various ranks, disciplines, and location of the college in the province. The Reflexive Thematic Analysis resulted in four themes: Policy-practice gap as institutional amnesia, self-provision - privatising reasonable adjustment, adaptive pedagogy - no institutional scaffolding, and professional identity - structural exclusion. The research findings reveal that the policy-institutions interface of inclusive employment in Punjab is not due to imperfect policy implementation but rather stands for cases of non-institutionalisation of the policy. Completely new qualitative evidence is provided within the lower-middle-income South Asian setting, while there are direct implications for the Higher Education Department, Punjab, and the Higher Education Commission, Pakistan.

Keywords: *Visual Impairment, Inclusive Employment, College Teaching, Policy-Practice Gap, Reflexive Thematic Analysis, Institutional Barriers, Punjab, Pakistan*

1. Introduction

The issue of 'disability inclusion in higher education' has found a growing space and salience in international policy-making since the formulation of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD), which commits signatories to equal employment opportunities for persons with disabilities. Inclusive employment in the public college sector, however, is formalised within a policy framework in Pakistan, as the country is a signatory to the UNCRPD since 2011, and since then has enacted a series of policy instruments, most

notably the Higher Education Commission's disability policy (HEC, 2021), the National Gender Policy Framework (NGPF, 2022) and the Punjab Empowerment of Persons with Disabilities Act 2022 (Government of the Punjab, 2022). This framework matters for those it protects yet remains understudied. However, ample evidence illustrates how, even with the enactment of disability policy, those policies do not necessarily lead to institutional change, both in high- and low-income countries; although evidence of the disconnect between policy and practices around students with disabilities has been collected at length, few empirical studies exist to document the policy to practice gap when it comes to teaching faculty in lower-middle-income (LMI) South Asian contexts (Sang et al., 2022).

The public colleges in Punjab are controlled by the Higher Education Department of Punjab and the Higher Education Commission of Pakistan. Both bodies have issued instructions regarding disability inclusion, and in 2025, the Lahore High Court issued instructions for the Punjab government to implement the three percent disability ratios in employment in response to "deficiency in institutionalisation" (Sheikh, 2026). This is a legal action indicating the severity of the actual implementation problem and that the experiences of visually impaired employees in colleges are now becoming an empirical issue. However, the current research conducted in Pakistan focuses more on the accessibility issues of students with disabilities and their experience as learners rather than the experience of disabled faculty (Ayub, 2021). Qualitative studies have not yet investigated the daily working context of the visually impaired college teachers, such as receiving orientation, accommodation, accessible infrastructure, or getting professional development support.

This study addresses this gap. This study aims to find the link between inclusive employment policy and the lived experiences of visually impaired college teachers in public colleges in Punjab. The inquiry is structured around three research questions. First, what is the college teaching staff with visual impairment doing to implement inclusive employment policies within their professional work? Second, how do visual impairment college teachers experience inclusive employment policies? Third, what institutional practices help or hinder the professional development of visually impaired teaching staff? These questions arise from the theoretical perspective of the social model of disability, which locates disability in social organisation, not the individual impairment, and are answered using Reflexive Thematic Analysis as the method of analysis.

The paper proceeds as follows: a thematic review of the literature, a methodology section, a section of the results which includes four superordinate themes, a discussion, and a conclusion.

2. Literature Review

2.1 The Policy-Practice Gap in Disability Inclusion

There is a clear gap between disability and higher education policy and practice, as reported in the literature. Regarding employment, although legal frameworks take the UNCRPD approach and impose obligations from a rights perspective, research in various national contexts shows that these obligations are not consistently reflected in institutional behaviour. Although US academic institutions have policy frameworks designed to address accessibility barriers, such barriers persist. It is usually asserted that the focus on compliance must be replaced by buy-in from university leaders as they resource and shift the institutional culture. This observation reflects a central premise of the literature: policy can be necessary but not

sufficient for inclusion, and the gap between policy and practice does not occur because of legislative deficiency but because institutional actors create and sustain it.

The findings from South Asia are consistent with this conclusion and provide a valuable level of specification. One qualitative study in Bangladesh indicated that although an integrated inclusive education approach was absent in the country's public universities, there was a formal commitment to inclusive education, but support provision was irregular, facilities were not accessible, and no integrated approach was taken to inclusive education provision (Sayem & Bhuiyan, 2025). The welfare model predominates in Pakistan and neighbouring countries, whereas the rights-based approach remains underdeveloped, which is the primary structural barrier to the Convention's implementation (Chaudhary & Sharma, 2026). Several studies have specifically studied the HEC policy 2021 and revealed that the policy was bringing minor benefits to students with disabilities, but at the same time, most institutions had no education, training, resources, or coordination in terms of fulfilling the policy (Manzoor et al., 2025; Manzoor et al., 2024). However, it is important to note that the study only focused on students, as the disabled faculty members' professional experiences were not addressed.

This gap is compounded by the methodological limitations of current literature. Survey design and mixed methods can only describe the reality or lack of the reality of policy provision and yield no insight into the lived experience of implementation in the minds of professionals with disabilities (Sniatecki et al., 2015). The only way to shed light on the mechanisms of production and maintenance of such gaps in the working lives of certain individuals is through qualitative approaches, which is the aim of this study.

2.2 Professional Experiences of Disabled Academic Staff

There is far less research on the working lives of disabled academics as opposed to their academic student lives. Sang et al. (2022) study with 75 disabled academics in the United Kingdom showed that, based on the social relational model of disability, disability is socially constructed and represented in the workplace through human resource management in the processes of negotiating access to the academy, negotiating a career, and negotiating workplace adjustments. They found that policies to support disabled staff at their institutions tended to reinforce the inequalities they were aiming to tackle and hinged on the goodwill of individual managers rather than on a commitment from the institutions to support disabled staff. This reframing is analytically significant from a personal state to an institutional phenomenon.

However, disabled faculty across the globe consistently faced poor organisational expectations, limited professional development opportunities, and informal, instead of formalised support arrangements. The review was able to pinpoint an additional gap: the literature mainly consists of studies of high-income (HEC, 2021)—anglophone contexts with little evidence from LMI contexts, such as Pakistan. However, Altstadt, D'Souza and Alex (2025) confirmed this, finding that so often the disabled professional students had been expected to manage the inaccessibility alone—in what they termed an invisible tax on professional time and energy and an absorptive cost borne privately by individual faculty members whose institutions nominally claimed to include them. The overall background of the present study is given by these findings: The context of the empirical study of the present study is that the visually impaired teachers working in the colleges of Punjab are in a situation

that is not only under-resourced but is also a culture of an institution that is not subject to accountability for what it produces, as far as the professional situation is concerned.

2.3 Assistive Technology and the Accessible Academic Workplace

Assistive technology plays a pivotal role in the academic functioning of the visually impaired. Well-supported screen-reading software and text-to-speech tools have the potential to greatly enhance the professional functioning of a visually impaired teacher (İşlek, 2026). International literature clearly shows, however, that there is considerable variation in institutional access, and that it is important to have access, as well as training, technical support, and the availability of digitally accessible content.

These findings align with Pakistani studies documenting barriers faced by visually impaired scholars, such as the unavailability of screen-reading software licences in higher education institutions, lack of training on assistive tools, and inaccessibility of digital course materials and content by visually impaired scholars (Hussain, 2022). The same holds true for the documentation of the digital accessibility environment; even though that study was focused on students, it has direct implications for faculty teaching in digital environments. Even in US higher education environments, screen-reader users encountered consistent problems and barriers related to physical materials for classrooms lacking electronic alternatives, digital content lacking accessibility, or software-based platforms that did not support the screen-readers (Kirboyun Tipi, 2026). These results help to define the structural indicators of institutional commitment: if an institution lacks access to assistive technology, it indicates that the professional and technical needs of the visually impaired staff are not incorporated in daily governance or in the agenda of the institution.

2.4 Institutional Culture, Accountability, and Street-Level Bureaucracy

This way of thinking about the failure of policy commitments to lead to change is analytically productive through Lipsky's (2010) theory of street-level bureaucracy. Lipsky (2010) argues that policy is enacted by practitioners, not legislated text, and that street-level bureaucrats (including institutional leaders) routinely adapt, dilute, and disregard policy under conditions of limited resources and limited accountability (Lipsky, 2010). In the context of disability inclusion, this describes how college principals and administrators may serve as unwitting agents of null policies and practices when they are unaware of what disability inclusion requires, how to pay for it, or how it is evaluated. Schreuer et al. (2024) concluded that only the institutional culture and the disposition of academic leadership and disability coordinators extended to disabled staffing really mattered in the provision of reasonable accommodations and that the different experiences were interpreted as a result of different cultures within the same country and under the same policy. Barnes (2019) argue that disability is produced by institutional organisation: disabled conditions are created upon the organisation of institutional practice, not by individual impairment.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The research design used was qualitative and interpretive. Reflexive Thematic Analysis approach was used for the analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2022). Reflexive TA is consistent with the theoretical stance of the study: That meanings are co-constructed between participants and researchers, rather than discovered within the data as pre-existing patterns. It is flexible theoretically and allows for the social model of disability to inform thematic

interpretation and not set up the framework for the use thereof. It generates pattern-level insight across participants, which was appropriate for the dataset of ten interviews focused on three common research questions. The epistemological position of this study is opposed to positivist assumptions. Themes are "built" by the researcher based on a process of "interpretive engagement" with the data and are not "out there" in the data, waiting to be struck upon.

3.2 Philosophical Paradigm

The ontology of this study is "relativist": Realities are multiple, constructed, and context-dependent. The epistemological approach is constructionist. The knowledge of the professional experience of visually impaired university teachers is not directly accessible to anyone; it is created through the interpretations of the participants involved. This constructionist view of language considers the participants' accounts as acts of language that 'construct' meanings of their experience through language, not as windows on institutional facts. The analytic approach is mainly experiential and aims to gain insights into the processes of constructing and sense-making of participants over their professional world, and that are critically influenced by the social model approach to disability in later analytic stages.

3.3 Analytic Approach

The analysis was inductive in the early stages, using codes that emerged from the language used and problems of interest among the participants. Later analytical stages (from Phase 3) applied the social model of disability as an interpretive approach to assist in assigning interpretive meaning to codes and themes. The main focus was a latent one: In addition to the first-order meaning, which is conveyed by the participant's actual words, the analysis was concerned with the second-order meaning, the conditions and assumptions embedded in the first-order meaning of the accounts.

3.4 Participants and Sampling

The participants were selected based on the formulation of the criteria to be used in the study, which is sampling based on Patton (2015), as purposive sampling. The inclusion criteria were as follows: participants should have a recognised teaching status in a public or semi-government college in Punjab, a confirmed diagnosis of visual impairment (partial or total), and at least one year of teaching experience at the college level. These criteria enabled the identification of an appropriate level of institutional experience to be able to respond in meaningful ways to the criteria examined. The number of selected participants from various colleges and various districts of Punjab was ten. They hailed from different academic positions ranging from Lecturer to Full Professor, different faculties such as Education, Urdu Literature, History, Psychology and Political Science and different service durations ranging from about 2 to 30 years. It was a sample of urban and semi-rural male and female participants (Creswell & Poth, 2023). The sample size was justified by information power, and by the well-defined aim, specific target group of participants, experienced theoretical approach and cross-case analysis (Malterud et al., 2016) that were applied in the study.

3.5 Data Collection

Use of semi-structured interviews, whereby each participant was interviewed individually to produce data. Based on the literature and the research questions, an interview guide was created, which consisted of open-ended questions related to initial employment experience, professional activities, usage of assistive technology, institutional support, experience with

inclusive employment policies, and suggestions for institutional change. The interviews were similar in nature for all participants, with a duration of approximately 45 to 90 minutes, and were held in Urdu or English, depending on the participants' preference, and were audio-recorded with participants' consent. Any recordings were transcribed word for word, and a transcript was checked against a recording for accuracy. At transcription, participant names were replaced with pseudonyms (Participant-01 to Participant-10), and any institutional and/or personally identifying information in transcripts was obscured before analysis.

3.6 Data Analysis Procedures

The six stages of Reflexive TA directed analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2022) were followed. In Phase 1, the first researcher read all ten transcripts and made notes in an electronic reflexive journal. In Phase 2, the researcher systematically coded all transcripts using descriptive and interpretive codes without excluding any of the data. Phase 3 clustered codes into tentative themes. Phase 4 involved comparing the candidate themes with the entire dataset to evaluate cohesion, distinctiveness, and fit; the themes were merged and renamed as appropriate. In Phase 5, the final names and definitions of the themes were constructed, defining the central organising concept of each theme and how this related to the research questions and the social model of disability. Phase 6 used verbatim quotations, keeping description and interpretation distinct.

4. Findings

Four main themes resulted from the analysis. Each theme is presented with two or three sub-themes and illustrative quotations. The participant ID reflects a pseudonym that was given at the transcription.

4.1 Theme 1: Policy as Text, Not Practice

The overall issue of this theme is a total lack of institutional machinery for linking policy commitments with professional conditions. Institutions did not enact inclusive employment policies; instead, participants saw inclusive employment policy as text unknown to participants and supervisors.

4.1.1 No Orientation at Entry

All ten participants reported that they did not receive any disability-related orientation when they joined their respective institutions. Participant-01, a lecturer in education with approximately two and a half years of service experience, stated directly, "When we went to the workplace, as a handicapped or as a new person, I was not given any kind of proper formal information" (Participant-01). Participant-09, a full professor with almost 30 years of experience, noted that the Promotion-Linked Training by the Higher Education Department did not mention any aspect of discrimination with regard to disability: "Nothing is mentioned in the Promotion-Linked Training, done by the Higher Education Department, regarding disability in the workplace" (Participant-09). This level of normalisation of entry conditions, where visually impaired employees are treated identically to sighted staff, is the foundational institutional failure that forms the basis of all other barriers.

4.1.2 Institutional Ignorance of Policy Provisions

Every time participants interacted with principals, vice principals, and administrative officers, they consistently encountered administrators unaware of policy requirements that officially regulated their work lives. Participant-06, who was a lecturer in the History Department with eight years of experience at different public colleges in South Punjab, while conducting

various classes and giving speeches to the students, reported, "The Principal and the clerical staff often do not know this, bring us the evidence, we do not have any orders" (Participant-06). Participant-03, who is a Lecturer in Psychology, pointed out the structural reason: "If there are written policies, it is not known to the people receiving the policies, even if I know the written policies, they are not implemented at the institutional level as well, which is the job of the head of the institution to know which policies they have" (Participant-03). Participant-04, a Lecturer in Political Science at a women's college in Lahore, reported that at most only 5-10% of the policy could be seen in practice at the institutional level. These accounts suggest that the issue is not resistance but policy amnesia - there are policy documents, but mechanisms to get them to those who are expected to enact them are limited.

4.1.3 Quota Non-Implementation

Several participants directly addressed the three percent disability employment quota. Participant-06 stated, "There is a three per cent quota for special persons, but the government implements it only on paper" (Participant-06). Participant-07 stated that he had tried thrice to get a job at Punjab Public Service Commission but managed to get it on the basis of disability quota only, which occurred inconsistently. It is clear from the placement of Participants-09 and -06 (who got jobs but not quotas) that there was no systematic way of entering the job market, and the irregularity reflects inconsistent quota operationalisation.

4.2 Theme 2: The Private Economy of Reasonable Adjustment

This theme is organised on the basis of 'privatisation of institutional responsibility.' All ten participants managed, financed, or arranged their own professional support, meaning that they bore costs that legally belonged to the institution.

4.2.1 Self-Funded / Self-Organised Support

Paper marking was the most persistent structural border in all ten accounts. None of the participants had been assigned the responsibility of institutional support for marking. Participant-01 said, "It is a bitter reality that though the college has staff, they do not help us in any way; they have CTIs, non-teaching, non-gazetted staff." Participant-07 described the informal setup she had at home to do the marking:

My niece, who is in her second year in school, read this to me, and I will tell her how many marks to allocate for the question. She does this at home in the evenings. I have no other choice, as this time too, the college had not provided me any aid whatsoever. (Participant-07)

Participant-03 privately funded an assistant she called to college when needed and called her to the college when board writing or reading from printed material was necessary. Participant-01 affirmed this setup by telling his representative: "The college does not do one thing to help (hiring) an assistant, privately - on my own." (Participant-01). The transfer of reasonable adjustment responsibility from institution to individual is seen to have been passed on throughout all ten accounts, and marked by the absence of deliberate and intentional action, and funded through participants' own salaries.

4.2.2 Digital Inaccessibility

Digital infrastructure inaccessibility has led to the self-provisioning of administrative functions. The screen-reading software she had been trained on was not available on the college computers, as reported by Participant-01: "The college administration does not purchase software like JAWS or TALKS." Participant-08 shared an experience with an

institution that was running on paper and did not have a digital teacher portal. Participant-10 reported that a colleague brought in her data and made it accessible in institutional portals, an undocumented arrangement with no formal provision. These were not the result of policy but relied on personal relationships that could not be taken for granted.

4.3 Theme 3: Adaptive Pedagogy in Unsupported Classrooms

This theme is based on professional expertise developed and applied outside the context of institutions. An analytically important feature of the participants' resourcefulness is that it evidenced institutional default, not successful inclusion; the sophistication of these adaptations demonstrates the scale of institutional failure.

4.3.1 Memorisation, Relational Management, and Peer Networks

Strategies were created and developed in a logical manner across participants regarding managing the classroom without visual information. Participant-06 "memorised" seating arrangements, thus locating students by name. Several participants used Class Representative networks for attendance, material distribution, and classroom tasks that several participants used. For participant-05, it was a voice recognition system that was used as a classroom identification system. Participant-10, as a visiting lecturer in a semi-government institution in Lahore, explained how professional knowledge circulated informally among visually impaired peers who are visually impaired:

There was no formal induction related to assistive tools or classroom layout. I got the information from my colleagues on how to do it, as I am visually impaired. We have a sort of informal network. However, when it comes to something new in the institution, we are always the ones who are lagging behind, and that too only when the deadline is over. (Participant-10)

This story is the interpretive essence of this theme: The interpretive work of the participants (pedagogical expertise) is self-made, spread through peers, and lost within institutions. Participants' pedagogical expertise is self-made, peer-transmitted, and institutionally unrecognised.

4.3.2 Uneven Access to Assistive Technology

There was great variation in the access to assistive technology that each participant reported by institutional location. Those attending colleges in urban areas with positive experiences with digital infrastructure were more likely to report higher, but still variable, levels of access to screen-reading tools. Participant-06, from South Punjab, reported network connectivity challenges that further exacerbated software inaccessibility and created a "spatial inequality" that compounded an already structurally marginalised position. No professional training in assistive technology was identified in all ten accounts, confirming the gap between assistive technology provision and professional use as documented in Hussain et al.'s (2022) study.

4.4 Theme 4: Professional Identity Under Structural Exclusion

This theme is about professional belonging denied to visually impaired teachers in institutions that aim to employ them but never include them in their institutional life. Participants navigated the tension between demonstrated competence and institutional nonrecognition.

4.4.1 Competence Questioned at Entry

Multiple participants shared experiences with institutions' leaders who viewed visual impairment as presumptive incompetence. Participant-05 is a lecturer in Urdu Literature who recalled her first meeting with a college principal. "I had asked for accommodation, but I was

asked how I would teach?" (Participant-05). This question pre-emptively framed impairment as professional incapacity prior to Participant-05 even being in a classroom. This exposes the assumption involved in the operations of the institution, namely, that the professional ideal is sighted and that the visually impaired employee must prove professional equivalence.

4.4.2 Exclusion from Institutional Processes and Symbolic Spaces

In all ten accounts, exclusion from committees, institutional functions, and communication processes was reported. Participant-01 spoke about an institutional event but stated that she had no activity there and then felt very bad and down. In such meetings, Participant-06 noted that administrative committee meetings were invariably held with sighted members, and it would be better to have a blind person at a counselling/consultation level: "In such meetings, one feels excluded. The least of all, a blind person can be kept at counselling or consultation level in administrative committee meeting" (Participant-06). Participant-05 was told of a staff meeting having to take place only after it was already done, and she was not included in the staff communication group to which the meeting was communicated. These choices of exclusion take place both practically and symbolically at the same time. In practice, they prevent the visually impaired employees from accessing information in the institution. Symbolically, they indicate that for full professional membership, sensory abilities are necessary with institutional norms.

5. Discussion

5.1 Interpretation of Findings

The four themes form a coherent argument. Overall, they show that inclusive employment commitments in Pakistan's national and provincial policy framework are performative, meaning that they are present in policy but absent from college governance. This is not a gradational issue, but a structural one. Participants did not report any institutions attempting to accommodate resource-poor situations. They stated that the management of some institutions was not aware of the policy requirements for employing the visually impaired. Lipsky's (2010) street-level bureaucracy theory is the most fitting theory to grasp this result. Policy is enacted through the decisions of institutional actors. In this study, the college principals, vice principals, and administrative officers were not trained, not incentivised to implement, and not even given the distributed policy knowledge to do so. The outcome was 'institutional amnesia'—the policy was at the federal and provincial levels, but it was unknown at the college gate.

5.2 Connection to Existing Literature

The results are congruent and add to the international literature in several analytically fruitful ways: In the United Kingdom, institutional arrangements mirrored inequalities, as they relied on the goodwill of individual managers and not on systemic commitment (Sang et al., 2022). The present study confirms this finding (conducted in a vastly different institutional setting) and sharpens it: In Punjab colleges, the institutional leadership lacks a basic background to think of accommodation as a duty rather than as a discretionary act. Visually impaired faculty across institutions rely on informal rather than formalised support, supporting Merchant et al.'s (2020) finding that this applies to disabled faculty across high-income institutions, but in a more severe and under-researched form, in low-income institutions.

Theme 2's findings build on the disability tax developed by Altstadt et al. Accommodation costs are professional, domestic, and financial, borne from participants' salaries, and unpaid

labour has to be foregone by family members in the public colleges of Punjab. This is what the social model of disability has called disability produced by institutional organisation (Barnes, 2019): When the institution fails to make a reasonable adjustment, disability is created, and treating the resulting gap as an individual and family matter. The findings of theme two in terms of digital inaccessibility complement and build upon previous work in the Pakistani higher education context by Hussain et al. (2022) into the employment context.

5.3 Implications

The policy-practice gap on disability inclusion requires reconceptualisation. It is invariably defined today under the guise of some notion of "implementation quality" or "resource adequacy". This study indicates that for the college sector of Punjab, the gap lies at the moment of implementation or at least, it is a failure to embed policy in governance, accountability, and professional knowledge. Reform requires institutionalising existing policy, not revising it, so that a leadership development process is mandatory, disability issues form part of accountability measures in college inspections, and the task of orienting leaders becomes a formal requirement in the appointing process. Three practical entry points are identifiable: during the appointment process, where disability orientation should be mandatory; where accommodation compliance should form part of inspection criteria; and the teacher training programme, where rights-based disability inclusion should be embedded.

6. Conclusion

This study aimed to explore the relationship between inclusive education policy and the professional lives of visually impaired college teachers in public colleges in Punjab, Pakistan. Our research problem was focused on the fact that Pakistan has formal policy for inclusive employment, yet visually impaired college teachers report its absence at the institutional level, where it might have an impact. Focusing on the semi-structured interview data of ten participants who were interviewed using purposive sampling resulted in four major themes. Policy operates as text, not practice; reasonable adjustment is privatised, borne by the individual rather than the institution; adaptive pedagogy lacks an institutional platform, and professional identity is undermined by structural exclusion. Research questions were addressed in each theme, and the research problem was answered in general.

The significant part of these findings is that they contribute to knowledge on institutional disability inclusion in low-income institutional contexts. The study highlights that the implementation of inclusive policies and practices is incomplete, and there is a disjunction between the two in Punjab. The institution holds policy and legal mandates but neither reaches practice through governance or accountability. This finding suggests that reform must shift from policy development to institutionalising existing commitments, including leadership development programmes, use of a disability inclusion criterion as part of college inspections, disability-oriented induction at appointment, and monitoring of institutional leaders for orientation compliance. Together, these theoretical frameworks support this reorientation, locating disability in institutional organisation, not individual impairment.

Further studies should follow up on this cross-sectional study. For instance, longitudinal studies should track visually impaired teachers' career trajectories over time. A comparative study across institutional sectors would reveal the kind of structures that best predict the provision of inclusion in relation to governance and finances. Ultimately, the participants' resilience reflects competence in meeting institutional failure, not individual exceptionalism.

Inclusive employment in Punjab's colleges is not a future aspiration; it is an unfulfilled legal obligation.

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